

ANIMA

Aviation Noise Impact Management
through Novel Approaches

D6.13 Roadmap Version 3

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769627

Project Information	
PROJECT ID	769627
PROJECT FULL TITLE	Aviation Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches
PROJECT ACRONYM	ANIMA
FUNDING SCHEME	RIA – Research and Innovation action
START DATE OF THE PROJECT	01.10.2017
DURATION	48 months
CALL IDENTIFIER	H2020-MG-2017-SingleStage-INEA
PROJECT WEBSITE	www.anima-project.eu
Deliverable Information	
DELIVERABLE N° AND TITLE	D6.13 Roadmap V3
TYPE OF DELIVERABLE¹	R
DISSEMINATION LEVEL²	PU (except Annex 2, which is CO)
BENEFICIARY NUMBER AND NAME	7. ANOTEC
AUTHORS	Nico van Oosten
CONTRIBUTORS	E. Kors (SAE) ; S.Moal (AIF) ; R. Jaron (DLR) ; R. Aalmoes (NLR) ; S. Bartels (DLR) ; A. Wilson (ISVR) ; F. Cléro (ONERA) ; E. Bouty (SHE)
WORK PACKAGE N°	6
WORK PACKAGE LEADER	Eugene Kors
WP LEADER VALIDATION DATE	25/01/2022
COORDINATOR VALIDATION DATE	28/01/2021
COORDINATOR SIGNATURE	

¹ Use one of the following codes: R=Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC=Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER=Software, technical diagram, etc.

² Use one of the following codes: PU=Public, fully open, e.g. web
CO=Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement
CI=Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

Version follow-up		
Update	Name	Version
13/12/2021	Nico van Oosten	V1

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	5
2	Roadmap structure	6
2.1	<i>Subsets.....</i>	6
2.2	<i>Format</i>	6
2.2.1	Data structure	7
2.2.2	High-level roadmap format	9
2.2.3	Topic data sheets	9
2.2.4	Timelines	11
2.3	<i>Definition of maturity level.....</i>	11
3	Elaboration of Roadmap V3	15
3.1	<i>Review of roadmap V2.....</i>	15
3.2	<i>Scenario simulations in support of the roadmap.....</i>	15
3.3	<i>Consultation process.....</i>	16
3.4	<i>Final roadmap V3</i>	16
	Annex 1 High-level roadmaps.....	17
	Annex 2 Topic datasheets.....	25

1 Introduction

ANIMA Task 6.1 is dedicated to the definition and update of a common strategic research roadmap for aviation noise reduction, involving all key aspects related to mitigation solutions, assessment of noise effects on populations and community engagement.

In the past, strategic research roadmaps have been elaborated, mainly for aircraft noise reduction technology and, more recently, management of aviation noise impact. These roadmaps have been defined and maintained as an essential part of the work of the X-Noise network, funded through subsequent Coordination Actions in FP5, FP6 and FP7. However, in H2020 this network was no longer funded, and the maintenance of the roadmaps was stalled, until some funding became available in ANIMA to resume this work.

In ANIMA Deliverable D6.3, a first version of a new set of roadmaps was presented. A new structure of subsets was developed, together with the design of a new, common, format. Since the enlarged scope with non-technology related topics, the standard Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scaling needed to be extended to reflect also the maturity level of these topics.

In D6.8 several improvements to the first version of the roadmaps were included:

- A harmonised definition of the maturity scale
- Addition of a roadmap for UAV development
- Description of subtopics

After the release of D6.8 the roadmaps have been reviewed and updated where needed. Also missing information was added where possible.

In ANIMA a scenario-based revision process of the common roadmap was introduced. It was envisaged that the results from the scenario calculations V2 (presented in D4.10) would inform this process. However, due to time constraints the assessment of these results (D4.13 and D6.11) became available very late, due to which it was not possible to consider these as a source of information for the update process. These deliverables were therefore mainly used to check whether the latest available roadmaps are compatible with the findings of the scenario simulations.

The present document presents the final version (V3) of the roadmaps, as elaborated in ANIMA.

2 Roadmap structure

In D6.3, a new roadmap structure has been developed to arrive at a common strategic research roadmap. This structure is repeated to facilitate comprehension of the current report.

2.1 Subsets

For the first version of the common strategic roadmap for aviation noise research, 7 subsets were defined. After presentation of this first version to the Advisory Board, they recommended the inclusion of a subset for UAV development. This extension was taken up in the current version of the roadmap (Figure 2-1).

Figure 2-1 – Subsets of the common strategic roadmap for aviation noise research

Each subset was assigned to a relevant expert within the ANIMA/X-Noise European Aviation Noise Network, each forming a small task group to identify the research topics to be included in the corresponding subset.

Subset	Subset leader
Technology Development	S. Moal (Airbus)
Supersonic Aircraft	R. Jaron (DLR)
UAV Development	E. Bouty (Safran)
Airport Noise Management & Indicators	R. Aalmoes (NLR)
Impacts Understanding	S. Bartels (DLR)
High Fidelity Methods	A. Wilson (ISVR)
Experimental Techniques	F. Cléro (ONERA)
Exposure Tools & Metrics	N. van Oosten (ANOTEC)

2.2 Format

A new format was designed, considering especially the following requirements:

- *Ease of maintenance*
 The different subsets should be easy to maintain, so updates can be made available without too much effort. Potential future automation of the generation of the roadmaps should be considered.
- *Scalable*

The addition of new topics, an extra level of detail, or an extension of the horizon should be easy to handle.

- *Understandable by wider audience*

The roadmap should be visually attractive and should be understandable for an audience, beyond the current experts, such as policy makers or even the general public. Especially the latter may support the message that the aviation industry assigns significant resources in a well-organised research effort to reduce aviation noise and its impact.

2.2.1 Data structure

The following common structure for the contents of each roadmap has been defined, at present consisting of 4 levels:

Level	Element	Description	Example
1	Group	High level grouping, related to most relevant organisation type (industry, research centres, etc) – since this has a direct link with the committee that is charged with its maintenance (see section 4)	“Technology Contributors”
2	Subset	Logical grouping as presented in Fig. 3-1	“Technology Development”
3	Topic	Domains within each subset, that form a logical set of elements to be developed	“Low noise airframe design”
4	SubTopic	Particular field of research within a Topic	“Low noise Landing Gear Design and integration”

For each SubTopic several attributes have been defined:

Attribute	Description
Target maturity level at end of period	The maturity level that is envisaged to be reached by 2020, 2025, 2030 and 2035
Current status	A short description of historical milestones and the status at which the specific field of research is at this moment
Vision	A short description of how it is envisaged that this field of research should develop, which milestones have to be considered, and, if applicable, which other fields of research need to be resolved to reach maturity for real world implementation.
Related projects	Past and current EU and national projects that have contributed to the knowledge in this SubTopic and their end date

Although this structure is easily scalable towards even more detailed levels, here it is considered sufficient to elaborate down to SubTopic level. An Excel file was then created with the aim to capture in an easy manner all elements of each subset (see Figure 2-2).

Roadmap for: Airport Noise Management		Version: 14/10/2019				Related projects and year	
Topic	Subtopic	Target SRL at end of period			Current status		Vision
		2015-2020	2020-2025	2025-2030		2030-2035	
Qualified Balanced Scorecard for QoL	Refine QoL indicators	2-3	3-4	5-6	6-7	Based on literature research a number of indicators has been identified within ANIMA. Those indicators are currently on a global and abstract level. It is not clear yet what exactly the different indicators imply.	A comprehensive overview of corresponding measures and factors within each indicator should be worked out. This kind of overview could be some kind of matrix with a large number of factors corresponding to each quality of life indicator. Depending on the development and status of an airport, individual combinations of factors within the different indicators can be used to describe the level of quality of life around airports and areas of development can be identified.
	Making QoL indicators measurable (KPIs)	1	2-3	4-5	6-7	Currently factors describing different QoL indicators in detail are not available.	Measurable QoL indicators will grant an additional dimension of information besides dB levels, noise contours and technical recommendations from air traffic control centers. Measurable QoL indicators could be very helpful for decision making processes.
	Comparison/Weighting of QoL	1	2-3	4-5	6-7	There are no guidelines or recommendations available allowing the weighting and comparison of QoL indicators around airports.	Weighting of QoL indicators will help to compare the level of QoL for different areas around airports. This can be valuable information for the monitoring of interventions and the decision making process and the choice of interventions. Weighting and comparing different QoL indicators and corresponding factors should be possible on European level.
	Environmental impact		2-4	5-6	6-7	A qualified balanced scorecard does currently not exist. Typically, the number of highly annoyed or sleep disturbed people or noise contour areas are used to describe the environmental impact of aviation.	The environmental impact of aviation should include more global assessment such as the impact of CO2 and NOx. Simultaneously, the local impact of the LTO cycle around airports concerning local air quality should be assessed. A balanced score card should be available for the assessment.

Figure 2-2 – Example Excel sheet with data structure

2.2.2 High-level roadmap format

A first level of roadmaps was defined for each subset with the aim to obtain a visually attractive design, which can be used for dissemination purposes, and at the same time provides a concise overview of the topics and subtopics of each subset. An example of this high-level format is given in Figure 2-3.

Figure 2-3 – Example of a high-level roadmap

2.2.3 Topic data sheets

A second level of roadmaps was defined, consisting of a datasheet for each topic, containing the corresponding subtopics and the additional information on these:

- Short description of the current status
- A description of the vision how to reach full maturity
- The target maturity levels over time, required to fulfil the vision
- Related projects

Due to the rather detailed information in these datasheets, the target audience will mainly be restricted to direct stakeholders.

An example of such datasheet is presented in Figure 2-4.

High Fidelity Methods		
Noise Generation		
Broadband Aerofoil Response		
Current status	Turbulence generation and broadband acoustic response are usually calculated independently, typically with a partially scale-resolving code to predict the turbulence (previous section) and a linear CAA code for the response.	Projects:
Vision towards final TRL	Increased availability of high performance computing to increase take-up. Development of high order RANS-based methods to reduce cost of acoustic propagation.	
Full System Tone Noise Prediction		
Current status	Tones emanating from components are widely calculated in research and industry using Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) calculations. The number of full system calculations is limited by computational expense.	Projects:
Vision towards final TRL	Increased availability of high performance computing. Development of high order linear CAA codes for internal propagation with complex geometry. Improved models of wall treatments & acoustic liners when not modelled explicitly. In the longer term propagation codes able to model the effect of unsteady mean flows on acoustic propagation and fully coupled codes combining turbulence generation and response.	
Vortex/Blade Interaction		
Current status	These calculations are generally only performed at high fidelity in research programmes due to the computational expense of modelling vortex propagation.	Projects:
Vision towards final TRL	Improved turbulence models for vortex propagation and/or bespoke methods such as vorticity-preserving schemes.	
Combustion & Entropy Noise Sources		
Current status	These noise sources are less well understood, and calculations (typically partially spatially-resolved) are used to help identify source mechanisms.	Projects:
Vision towards final TRL	Further development of multi-physics codes and/or embedded empirical models for unsteady heat release. High quality experimental data at component level (combustor or turbine blade). Accurate source breakdown for validation data at full engine scale. Better source Models for transmission of noise through turbines.	

Figure 2-4 – Example of a topic datasheet

2.2.4 Timelines

To support the use of the roadmaps in e.g. the definition of research funding work programmes, the same information as provided in the above format is normally presented in the form of timelines. Although it was originally envisaged that a new format would be developed for this, it was finally considered that its added value does not compensate the resources required to generate and maintain this additional format. Timeline information is available in the topic datasheets. For public presentation the same format as developed in the X-Noise network projects (Figure 2-5) will continue to be used for the timelines.

Figure 2-5 – Example of a roadmap in timeline format

2.3 Definition of maturity level

The development of new technologies and methods requires in most cases a long time to mature. Typically, a decade or more may pass from the first idea up to a full-scale validation under operational conditions, so as to be ready for adoption in real life. It is therefore necessary to divide the development cycle in several stages, defining successive milestones, representing logical steps towards full maturity.

For technology related research and development, the well-known Technology Readiness Level (TRL) was therefore defined. However, for other domains, usually less related to the development of “hardware”, the same description of the evolution of maturity is not appropriate. Since the aim of the present Task in

ANIMA is to elaborate a common roadmap for all relevant domains (the subsets), a common methodology is required to derive a maturity scale for all subsets.

After the elaboration of the first version of the common roadmap it was recognised that further harmonisation work was needed with respect to the maturity scale. Although the term “harmonised” was initially interpreted as “a single scale for all subsets”. It became clear very soon that this was not feasible, due to the very different characteristics of the research processes for the different subsets. It was then agreed that each subset may have its’ own scale, but that this should be based on a generic maturity scale definition, to which only the minimum required adaptations should be made to represent the evolution of the research process of each subset. Figure 2-6 presents this generic scale description.

Level	Generic description
1	Basic principles observed and reported
2	Concept and/or application formulated
3	Proof-of-concept
4	Small-scale validation in laboratory environment
5	Small-scale validation in relevant environment
6	Prototype demonstration in a relevant environment
7	Prototype demonstration in an operational environment

Figure 2-6 – Generic description of the harmonized maturity scale

Once the generic description was agreed upon, a scale definition was developed for each subset (Figures 2-7 to 2-9). For the impact-related subsets the existing Societal and Knowledge Readiness Levels were evaluated as a starting point.

Level	Technology Development Supersonic Aircraft UAV Development
1	Basic principles observed and reported
2	Technology concept and/or application formulated
3	Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof-of-concept
4	Component and/or breadboard validation in laboratory environment
5	Component and/or breadboard validation in relevant environment
6	System/subsystem model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment
7	System prototype demonstration in an operational environment

Figure 2-7 – Maturity scale for Technology related subsets
 (Technology Development, Supersonic Aircraft and UAV Development)

Level	Airport Noise Management
1	creating awareness of stakeholders, educating stakeholders, adoption of balanced approach, collecting evidence to support findings
2	Community engagement strategies in addition to balanced approach, defining benefits from adaptive LUP
3	Proof-of-concept based on literature and pilot studies to test proposed strategies
4	Validation within laboratory and field studies and pilot studies
5	Validation through a variety of field studies
6	Comparison of theoretical findings and empirical research on noise strategy approaches - iterative feedback and if needed re-evaluation
7	Proposal of guidelines, recommendations and methods to compare different approaches

Level	Impacts Understanding
1	creating awareness of stakeholders, educating stakeholders, adoption of balanced approach, collecting evidence to support findings
2	Community engagement strategies in addition to balanced approach, defining benefits from adaptive LUP
3	Proof-of-concept based on literature and pilot studies to test proposed strategies
4	Validation within laboratory and field studies and pilot studies
5	Validation through a variety of field studies
6	Comparison of theoretical findings and empirical research on noise strategy approaches - iterative feedback and if needed re-evaluation
7	Proposal of guidelines, recommendations and methods to compare different approaches

*Figure 2-8 – Maturity scale for Impact related subsets
(Airport Noise Management & Indicators and Impacts Understanding)*

Level	High Fidelity Methods
1	N/A
2	N/A
3	Demonstrated capability of HiFi CFD/CAA method to capture underlying physics.
4	Validation against laboratory / low Reynolds Number experimental data or already validated CFD/CAA results.
5	Validation against data from simplified but otherwise representative geometry (e.g. 2D blade section).
6	Validation for a fully representative geometry in a relevant environment at reasonable compute cost.
7	Wide application within the research community.

Level	Experimental Techniques Exposure Tools
1	Basic setup to demonstrate the principle of the method
2	Demonstration of the method capabilities on simple setup
3	Validation of the method to characterise simple configurations at small scale with reference data
4	Validation of the method to characterise representative geometry at small scale
5	Validation of the method on representative component and environment at large scale
6	Validation of the method on representative subsystem model and environment at large scale
7	Method usable with limited number of parameters and graphic user interface

*Figure 2-9 – Maturity scale for Enablers subsets
(High Fidelity Methods, Experimental Techniques and Exposure Tools & Metrics)*

3 Elaboration of Roadmap V3

3.1 Review of roadmap V2

The first two versions of the roadmap were published in D6.3 and D6.8. Since the release of V2 the subsets have been maintained by the corresponding groups, mainly revising some sub-topics or timelines, considering new developments that occurred. In addition, the list of projects relevant for the different sub-topics has been enhanced.

3.2 Scenario simulations in support of the roadmap

At the start of ANIMA a scenario-based process was developed, in support of the roadmap development. A first round of scenarios was executed, resulting in deliverable D4.3. The results were assessed in D6.6 and it was concluded that due to various limitations in the scenario cases, it would be premature to use these results to inform the roadmap V2. For the next (and final) round of roadmap, leading to version V3, the scenario-based process was significantly enhanced. Figure 3-1 present the deliverables involved in this process. The objective of this scenario-based approach is to provide a complete overview of the effect of the planned research and its possibilities of achieving the goals set by ACARE from the standpoint of environmental constraints.

Figure 3-1 – Scenario process

D6.15 defines a complete set of cases, covering all relevant aspects of the Balanced Approach and taking into consideration the recommendations made in the assessment of the first round of scenario calculations (D6.6). These cases were executed with the Noise Management Tool Chain of WP4 and results were reported in D4.10. These results were assessed from a tool point of view, providing recommendations for future work (D4.13). In D6.11 a further assessment of the results was made. This assessment takes into consideration criteria such as noise exposure, annoyance and sleep disturbance and noise-emissions interdependencies. With respect to the scope of ANIMA evaluation process, it is

however limited to traditional civil aviation, therefore excluding further evaluation of supersonic aircraft or UAVs. The results of the assessment were envisaged to be used to inform the update process of the common strategic research roadmap. However, due to time constraints the assessment of these results (D4.13 and D6.11) became available very late, due to which it was not possible to consider these as a source of information for the update process. These deliverables were therefore mainly used to check whether the latest available roadmaps are compatible with the findings of the scenario simulations.

3.3 Consultation process

The full update process is depicted in Figure 3-2.

Figure 3-2 – Roadmap update process

After the assessment of the scenario simulation results (presented in D6.11) a draft final version of the roadmap was presented to the full network meeting, with the aim to obtain feedback from the research community.

3.4 Final roadmap V3

The updated set of high-level roadmaps (V3) is provided in Annex 1.

The topic datasheets are contained in Annex 2. Due to its extension, Annex 2 is available in Excel format only. This Annex is considered Confidential information and is not distributed with the rest of D6.13.

Annex 1 High-level roadmaps

Technology Development

Operational Noise Abatement

- Enhanced Arrival/Departure Procedures
- Ground operations

Low noise airframe design

- Low noise Landing Gear Design and Installation
- Low noise wing and movables integration
- Aero acoustic scaled demonstration

Acoustic integration of high efficiency low emission unconventional propulsion systems

- Ducted Fan incl. Variable Pitch
- Propellers, Open Rotors & Unducted Fans
- Aeroacoustics of Boundary Layer Ingestions propulsion
- Distributed propulsion (with propellers)
- Electrification/hybridization

Aero-acoustic integration of UHBR turbofan propulsion system

- Advanced nacelle acoustic technologies
- Advanced flow physics simulation application to fan & turbomachinery
- Integrated low emission combustors
- Jet / Airframe interaction mitigation

Supersonic Aircraft

Sonic Boom Prediction

- Near&Far-field modelling & validation (cruise)
- Focus Boom modelling & validation
- Effects of atmosphere & topography on sonic boom
- Building response & indoor propagation

Low Boom Design

- Low boom demonstrator concept study
- Sensitivity effects off-design conditions
- Low LTO & Low boom tradeoffs

LTO Noise

- Advanced takeoff trajectory (PLR + fast climb out)
- Advanced engine technologies for LTO noise

Human Perception and Community Surveys

- Indoor & Outdoor simulators
- Loudness metrics for indoor and outdoor sonic boom
- Effect of sonic boom on sleep disturbance

Flight Procedures & Instrumentation

- Relevant Flight Procedures (cruise, focusing)

UAV Development

Noise source level

- Quick models for noise source evaluation
- Tests in anechoic wind tunnel for validation
- Scaling effect methodology
- Quiet component design

Aircraft level

- Shielding & Acoustic Installation Effects
- Noise mitigation systems
- Flight test demonstration

Propagation effects

- Ground effects in Urban Environment
- Integrated tools for in-flight aircraft prediction including complex trajectories / Urban environment
- Validate methodology through testing

Trajectory impact on Noise

- Propose methodology for defining low-noise impact trajectories, including:
 - Operational constraints
 - Trajectorial constraints
 - Fleet effects
- Investigate low-noise trajectories

Public acceptance

- Influence factors
 - (Psycho-)Acoustics
 - Non-acoustics
 - Fleet effects
- Acoustics metrics
- Impact indicators
- Strategies for low impact on citizens
- Regulation

High Fidelity Methods

Ben Kheil et al AIAA 2017-3012, ONERA

Turbulence (Precursor to Broadband Noise Generation)

- Turbulence - Wing, Aerofoil or Undercarriage
- Turbulence - Installed Jet & other Installation Sources
- Turbulence Development & Transition

Noise Generation

- Broadband Aerofoil Response
- Full System Tone Noise Prediction
- Vortex/Blade Interaction
- Combustion and Entropy Noise Sources

Wilson AIAA 2018-3776, ISVR

Noise Propagation & Radiation

- Blade row transmission, compressor and Turbine Noise
- Acoustic Liner
- Noise/Turbulence Interaction

Integrated Methods for Prediction and Design Optimisation

- Coupled Source / Propagation
- Coupled Mean flow / Turbulence Generation
- High Fidelity Multi-Disciplinary Design Optimisation

REBEL Configuration, courtesy of University Roma Tre

New Architecture

- Shielding & Acoustic Installation Effects (propagation)
- Long Range Propagation
- Ground Noise in an Urban Environment
- Electric Motor Self Noise
- Electric Motor / System Integration

Experimental Techniques

Velocity

- On single points
- In a section
- In the volume
- Time resolved

Density

- Qualitative data in single directions
- Quantitative data in single directions
- Quantitative data in the volume

Pressure

- Dynamic fluctuation on single points
- Mean values on a surface
- Dynamic fluctuations on a surface

Acoustics

- Steady state conditions in free field or anechoic room
- Transient conditions in free field or anechoic room
- In-duct modal detection
- In aerodynamic wind tunnel

Impacts Understanding and Counter Measures

Airport Response

- Improved Communication
- Airport Environmental Management
- Aviation contributions to CoL

Annoyance models

- Acoustical & Non-acoustical factors
 - Fixed wing
 - Multi-modal transport
 - Drones
 - Supersonic aircraft
 - General aviation
 - Helicopters
 - Electric flying (air taxi)

Sleep Models

- Sleep Disturbance
 - Fixed wing
 - Multi-modal transport
 - Supersonic aircraft
 - Electric flying (air taxi)
 - Helicopters
 - General aviation
 - Drones

Health Models

- Adults & Children
 - Fixed wing
 - Multi-modal transport
 - General aviation
 - Electric flying (air taxi)
 - Drones
 - Helicopters
 - Supersonic aircraft

Airport Noise Management & Indicators

Qualified Balanced Scorecard for QoL

- Refine QoL indicators
- Making QoL indicators measurable (KPIs)
- Comparison/Weighting of QoL
- Environmental impact

Community Engagement Strategy

- Information
- Empowerment
- Engage communities with airport decisions

Measureable Benefits of interventions of Land-Use planning

- Policy measures
- Noise reduction measures
- Noise masking measures
- Adaptive land-use planning
- Harmonization of European Land-Use planning measures

Exposure Tools & Metrics

Noise Exposure Models

- Improvements of Integrated Models
- Semi-empirical source noise models for conventional and future aircraft/powerplant
- Propagation models
- Cruise noise models

Impact models

- Virtual Resident
- Acoustical factors
- Non-acoustical factors

Audiovisual simulations

- Audio simulation tools
- Visualization tools

Interdependencies

- Noise vs. Fuel/CO2
- Noise vs. LAQ (NOx, PM,..)
- Noise vs. 3rd Party Risk

Metrics

- Acoustic metrics
- Impact indicators
- Land Use Planning indicators
- Interdependencies metric
- Metrics for Communication
- Monetisation

Annex 2 Topic datasheets

In the following the Topic datasheets are provided. It is noted that for a very few (sub)topics not all information is included. This is mainly due to the fact that for these (sub)topics no consensus has been reached yet within the corresponding task group.

These datasheets are available in Excel format upon request. The datasheets are considered Confidential information.

